

Adapting Large Language Models to Low-Resource Languages: The Case of Macedonian

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Abstract. In this paper, we introduce *VeziKaLLM*, a 4B-parameter language model adapted specifically for the Macedonian language. It is available at the following link. *VeziKaLLM* is developed through continued pretraining of the open-source Gemma 3 4B base model, leveraging its architecture while adapting it to the linguistic and syntactic structures unique to Macedonian. Given the significant underrepresentation of Macedonian in the realm of high-quality Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools and resources, our primary goal is to bridge this gap by creating a fluent, contextually aware, and computationally efficient foundation model. *VeziKaLLM* is designed to serve as a strong base for a variety of downstream tasks and to support the development of instruction- and reasoning-tuned models in the future. We provide an overview of the model development pipeline, covering training data, infrastructure, and evaluation strategies. To assess the model’s capabilities, we evaluate *VeziKaLLM* on a suite of core Macedonian language benchmarks and compare its performance with its base model and several larger Macedonian language models. The results demonstrate that *VeziKaLLM* performs competitively despite its smaller size, highlighting its efficiency and effectiveness in handling tasks specific to a low-resource language. Our findings affirm that continued pretraining is a viable and cost-effective approach for enhancing language model performance in underrepresented linguistic contexts, and we offer insights into how this method can be generalized to other low-resource languages.

Keywords: Large Language Models · Natural Language Processing · Continued Pretraining · Macedonian Language · Low-Resource Language

1 Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) have rapidly become foundational to a wide range of Natural Language Processing (NLP) applications, including machine

translation, question answering, summarization, and dialogue systems. Their ability to generalize from large-scale pretraining data has revolutionized NLP workflows and enabled a new era of task-agnostic, zero-shot, and few-shot learning. However, the overwhelming majority of these advancements have disproportionately benefited high-resource languages such as English, Chinese, and Spanish, where abundant text corpora and research attention have facilitated model development and evaluation.

In contrast, low-resource languages like Macedonian, spoken by approximately 2 million people and classified under the South Slavic family, continue to face underrepresentation in the NLP landscape. These languages suffer from limited availability of high-quality text data, fewer annotated benchmarks, and a lack of large-scale pre-trained models tailored to their linguistic characteristics. As a result, even the most capable general-purpose LLMs often perform poorly on tasks involving Macedonian, due to limited exposure during pretraining and a lack of domain-specific adaptation.

This research seeks to address these disparities by introducing *VezilkaLLM*, a 4B-parameter decoder-only language model specifically adapted to Macedonian through continued pretraining. Rather than training a new model from scratch, which is computationally expensive, we adopt a resource-conscious strategy by leveraging the existing capabilities of *Gemma 3 4B*, an open-source model originally released by Google DeepMind. *Gemma 3* provides a strong multilingual foundation with robust architecture and efficient attention mechanisms. By isolating the language model component and retraining it on Macedonian-specific data, we aim to bridge the performance gap in a practical and scalable manner. We make *VezilkaLLM* publicly available at the following link.

2 Related Work

Efforts to adapt large language models to low-resource languages have gained increasing attention, especially for underrepresented languages such as Macedonian. Our work on *VezilkaLLM* builds on this growing body of research.

Several studies have focused specifically on developing language models and resources for Macedonian. In [11], Krteski et al. introduce *domestic-yak*, an 8B-parameter model trained on the largest Macedonian corpus to date (40GB) and accompanied by a new evaluation suite. The model achieves strong benchmark results and receives favorable qualitative feedback from native speakers. In [4], Dobreva et al. present *MACEDONIZER*, the first contextualized language model for Macedonian, pre-trained on a 6.5GB corpus and evaluated on multiple downstream tasks. In [3], Bogdanoski et al. explore Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) for Macedonian using models like *Wav2Vec 2.0*, showing that speech models could also be adapted effectively. Our approach complements these by focusing on a smaller, computationally efficient model (4B parameters) and emphasizing continued pretraining for improved contextual understanding.

Continued pretraining has emerged as a practical strategy for enhancing LLMs in low-resource contexts. In [9], Joshi et al. apply this approach to Hindi

by combining synthetic and real bilingual corpora, demonstrating gains in both language-specific and general capabilities. In [7], Imani et al. scale this strategy across 511 languages using the Glot500 corpus, showing the effectiveness of broad horizontal scaling via continued pretraining. Our method draws on similar ideas but applies them specifically to Macedonian with targeted monolingual data and evaluation.

Several modular techniques have been explored for multilingual LLM adaptation. In [10], Khade et al. use LoRA PEFT tuning to adapt multilingual Gemma models to Marathi and observe trade-offs between reasoning and fluency. In [5], Gurgurov et al. investigate adapter-based tuning techniques for small multilingual models, finding them particularly effective for low-resource settings. In [8], Jiang et al. propose Franken-Adapter, a modular embedding surgery method that demonstrated scalable cross-lingual transfer with minimal performance loss in English. While VezilkaLLM does not currently incorporate adapter techniques, these works inform future directions for efficient multilingual adaptation.

The availability and quality of training and evaluation data are critical for model development. In [11], Krsteski et al. construct a Macedonian evaluation suite covering seven benchmarks, which we use to evaluate VezilkaLLM. In [6], Hettiarachchi et al. provide a broader overview of community efforts in the LoResLM 2025 workshop, highlighting trends in data collection and benchmark construction for low-resource languages. Similarly, [12] and [7] create large multilingual corpora and corresponding LLMs, reinforcing the importance of resource creation at scale.

Evaluation methodologies for low-resource languages remain an ongoing challenge. In [1], Al Nazi et al. assess multiple LLMs (open and closed-source) on Bengali using zero-shot, few-shot, and chain-of-thought prompting, and highlight the impact of hyperparameter tuning. In [14], Shi et al. survey continual learning challenges in LLMs, including catastrophic forgetting during domain adaptation, which is relevant when adapting models like Gemma for Macedonian. These studies support the use of diverse evaluation protocols, a direction we adopt in benchmarking VezilkaLLM.

In [2] and [13], the authors provide broader perspectives on low-resource language modeling, mapping development challenges and strategies across text and multimodal domains. These works underline the need for context-aware approaches, local involvement, and efficient methods – a perspective central to our motivation for developing VezilkaLLM.

In summary, our work builds upon existing efforts to enhance LLM performance in Macedonian and other low-resource languages through continued pretraining, resource-efficient architecture selection, and systematic evaluation. By aligning with these directions, VezilkaLLM contributes a practical and scalable solution to the broader goal of linguistic inclusion in NLP.

3 Model Architecture

The architecture of VezilkaLLM is based on the language model component of Gemma 3 4B, a model originally developed by Google DeepMind [15]. Gemma 3 itself is a multimodal model capable of processing both text and images, but for VezilkaLLM, we extract only the language model portion and use it for further development. This means that VezilkaLLM is purely a text-based model, without any of the vision capabilities found in the full Gemma 3 4B model. After isolating the LLM, we perform continued pretraining to adapt and enhance its performance in Macedonian.

VezilkaLLM uses a decoder-only transformer architecture, which is a common structure in modern large language models. It consists of approximately 4 billion parameters, placing it in the small-size category of current LLMs. The architecture incorporates rotary positional embeddings (RoPE), which help it handle very long sequences by encoding the position of tokens more efficiently.

The model includes several advanced features designed to enhance performance and training efficiency. The attention mechanism employs Grouped-Query Attention (GQA), a technique that allows for more efficient attention computation by sharing query projections across multiple heads. One of the key innovations inherited from Gemma 3 is its attention structure: VezilkaLLM follows a 5-to-1 ratio of local to global attention layers. Local attention layers use a sliding window approach to restrict the attention span and reduce memory use, while global layers attend over the full sequence to preserve long-range context. This combination strikes a balance between performance and efficiency.

The tokenizer used in VezilkaLLM is inherited directly from Gemma 3 and is based on SentencePiece. This tokenizer supports digit splitting, preserves whitespace, and operates at the byte level, making it well-suited for multilingual and noisy text. The vocabulary size is 262,000 tokens, which allows for flexible and compact text representation. Keeping the original tokenizer ensures compatibility with the broader Gemma ecosystem, including tools and checkpoints built around Gemma models.

In summary, VezilkaLLM is a text-only model derived from the Gemma 3 4B architecture. It retains the core language modeling innovations of Gemma 3 but omits the multimodal vision components. Through continued pretraining, we adapt it to the Macedonian language while maintaining architectural consistency with the original model.

4 Data

We conduct the continued pretraining of VezilkaLLM using the Macedonian Corpus [11], a large-scale, high-quality textual dataset specifically constructed to support natural language processing in Macedonian, a recognized low-resource language. Given the scarcity of digitized and linguistically coherent resources in Macedonian, the dataset addresses a critical gap by consolidating and filtering public text data from a wide variety of domains. The total dataset comprises approximately 16.78 GB of text, corresponding to around 1.47 billion words.

The corpus includes material drawn from major textual domains, such as online news outlets, digitized books, encyclopedic resources, academic publications, government documents, and user-generated content. The largest portion of the dataset is sourced from Hugging Face’s fineweb-2 corpus, which accounts for approximately 7.85 GB or 49.55% of the total data volume. This is followed by contributions from the HPLT-2 dataset (5.80 GB, or 36.87%), CLARIN - MaCoCu-mk version 2.0 (1.94 GB, or 12.39%), and the Macedonian Wikipedia (0.13 GB, or 0.83%). Additional smaller contributions include MMORE (0.04 GB, or 0.25%) and Mozilla’s Common Voice corpus (0.02 GB, or 0.12%). The diversity of these sources ensures broad coverage of vocabulary, styles, and domains.

For training purposes, the dataset was partitioned into training and validation sets in a 90:10 ratio. The partitioning strategy preserved proportional representation across data sources to maintain statistical coherence. The training subset was used during model optimization, while the validation set served for performance tracking, including perplexity evaluation and overfitting monitoring.

5 Training Setup

In this work, we perform full-weight continued pretraining of the Gemma 3 4B model, where we optimize all model parameters specifically for the next-token prediction task in Macedonian. This approach involves no freezing of layers and treats the pretrained Gemma model as a starting point. The objective is to adapt the model’s weights to the linguistic properties and patterns of Macedonian by minimizing the autoregressive language modeling loss. Formally, given a sequence of tokens $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_T)$, the model is trained to maximize the log-likelihood given by Eq. 1, where θ denotes the model parameters. This loss encourages the model to predict each token x_t based on its preceding context $x_{<t}$, thus learning a probability distribution over sequences that reflects the structure of the Macedonian language.

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta) = \sum_{t=1}^T \log P(x_t | x_{<t}; \theta) \quad (1)$$

To perform full-weight continued training of the Gemma 3 4B model on Macedonian data, we employ a single high-performance NVIDIA H100 GPU with 80 GB of VRAM, hosted on a dedicated workstation. The model is trained using the PyTorch Deep Learning (DL) framework, in conjunction with the Hugging Face Transformers and Accelerate libraries for seamless integration of large-scale model training workflows. To manage GPU memory efficiently and enable mixed-precision operations, we utilize support for bfloat16 arithmetic throughout training. This choice allows us to reduce memory usage and increase computational throughput, without sacrificing model accuracy or training stability.

Given the size of the model and the extended context length of 8192 tokens, we adopt a training regime that balances memory constraints with learning

efficiency. We conduct the training using a global batch size of 32, i.e., with a local batch size of 2 and gradient accumulation steps set to 16 to simulate a larger batch size across the limited hardware.

We use the AdamW optimizer, configured with 8-bit parameter quantization (via the BitsAndBytes library), which further reduce memory consumption and speeds up training. A cosine learning rate schedule is implemented with a small warmup phase at the beginning of training to help stabilize early optimization steps. The base learning rate is set to $2 \cdot 10^{-5}$, and a weight decay of 0.1 is applied to regularize the model and prevent overfitting. While the pretraining phase is limited to a single epoch over the entire dataset due to computational constraints, this strategy was sufficient to observe significant improvements in language modeling performance, as indicated by perplexity reductions and qualitative evaluation.

To ensure stability during long-sequence training, we apply gradient clipping (to a maximum norm of 1.0) to avoid exploding gradients. We configure checkpointing at regular intervals, every 1000 steps, to allow recovery in the event of hardware failures and to facilitate experimentation with intermediate model states. The entire training process was monitored using Weights & Biases (wandb), which tracked metrics such as training and validation loss, learning rate progression, and gradient norms in real time. This allowed us to fine-tune our hyperparameters and detect anomalies early in the training cycle.

Training time for one epoch spans approximately 240 hours, depending on I/O throughput and context length variability in the dataset. We save the final trained model in Hugging Face-compatible format for easy loading, inference, and integration into downstream tasks. Overall, the training setup focuses on maximizing model quality within a constrained compute environment, leveraging precision optimization, scheduling techniques, and careful memory management to successfully adapt a large language model to a low-resource linguistic setting.

6 Evaluation

To assess the performance of VezilkaLLM, we employ both intrinsic metrics and benchmark evaluations using a translated Macedonian NLP test suite. Intrinsically, the model is evaluated on perplexity, next-token prediction accuracy, and long-form generation quality. These tests are conducted on a held-out portion of the Macedonian corpus and use standard evaluation scripts adapted for long-context inference. Results show consistent improvements in text coherence, syntactic fluency, and vocabulary control compared to baseline models of similar size.

For benchmark evaluation, we rely on the Macedonian LLM Evaluation dataset [11]. This dataset covers a variety of reasoning and comprehension tasks, including common sense reasoning (HellaSwag, Winogrande, PIQA, OpenbookQA, ARC-Easy, ARC-Challenge) and reading comprehension (BoolQ). It is derived through a multilingual adaptation process, first selecting a high-quality Serbian benchmark (due to its linguistic proximity to Macedonian), then translating it

Table 1. Benchmark accuracy of VezilkaLLM, Gemma 3 4B, Domestic Yak 8B, and MKLLM 7B across seven Macedonian NLP tasks.

Task	gemma-3-4b-pt	VezilkaLLM	domestic-yak-8B	MKLLM-7B
ARC-Easy	0.4756	0.4983	0.5240	0.5425
ARC-Challenge	0.2841	0.3029	0.3140	0.3200
BoolQ	0.7474	0.7187	0.7676	0.7061
HellaSwag	0.3866	0.4133	0.4311	0.4307
OpenBookQA	0.2500	0.2500	0.2900	0.2800
PIQA	0.6192	0.6518	0.6670	0.6186
WinoGrande	0.5864	0.5935	0.6251	0.6188

using the Google Translate API. This is followed by refinement using GPT-4, significantly enhancing translation accuracy and fluency. A manual quality control pass confirms that the resulting Macedonian dataset is of high linguistic quality and faithful to the original benchmarks.

We compare VezilkaLLM against the base Gemma 3 4B and the Macedonian LLMs – MKLLM 7B and Domestic Yak 8B. We summarize the results in Table 1, and also visualize them in Figure 1. As observed, VezilkaLLM consistently outperforms the base Gemma 3 4B model across nearly all benchmarks, with the sole exception of BoolQ, where it performs slightly lower. Notably, VezilkaLLM achieves significant gains in commonsense reasoning tasks such as HellaSwag, PIQA, and Winogrande, highlighting its enhanced reasoning capabilities.

Furthermore, VezilkaLLM’s performance closely approaches that of the larger MKLLM 7B and Domestic Yak 8B models, despite being smaller in size. This demonstrates the effectiveness of our training and adaptation strategies in maximizing model efficiency without compromising task performance.

Overall, these results establish VezilkaLLM as a competitive and resource-efficient model for Macedonian NLP applications, balancing strong performance with moderate model complexity.

7 Limitations

While VezilkaLLM demonstrates strong performance for a low-resource language model, it has several limitations that must be acknowledged. First and foremost, the model is a base language model and has not undergone instruction tuning or alignment procedures such as Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF). As a result, it is not optimized for task-specific behaviors like following user instructions, answering questions reliably, or maintaining conversational coherence across multi-turn interactions. This limits its immediate utility in user-facing applications such as chatbots or virtual assistants.

Another key limitation is the absence of safety, moderation, or value-alignment layers. VezilkaLLM has not been explicitly filtered or aligned to avoid generating harmful, biased, or offensive content. Consequently, it may reproduce toxic language, stereotypes, or misinformation present in its training data. This makes

Fig. 1. Graphical comparison of model accuracy across Macedonian NLP benchmarks, highlighting VeziikaLLM’s performance relative to baseline and larger models.

the model unsuitable for deployment in environments where content moderation and ethical considerations are critical.

Additionally, despite the diverse data sources used in pretraining, the model may still struggle with specialized domains such as legal, medical, or technical texts, where terminology is dense and context-specific. The lack of domain-adaptive fine-tuning means performance in such areas may be suboptimal. Furthermore, factual hallucination remains a challenge: like many autoregressive models, VeziikaLLM can generate plausible-sounding but incorrect information, especially in open-ended generation tasks.

Finally, the evaluation suite used for benchmarking, though carefully translated and refined, is derived from existing multilingual datasets and may not fully capture the unique linguistic or cultural nuances of Macedonian. Future efforts should involve the creation of native Macedonian benchmarks and more rigorous human evaluations to assess real-world performance.

Addressing these limitations will involve further work, including instruction tuning, safety alignment, and domain-specific fine-tuning. These steps are essential to ensure the model is both performant and trustworthy in practical applications.

8 Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper, we present VeziikaLLM, a 4B-parameter Macedonian language model derived from the Gemma 3 architecture through continued pretraining. Targeting a significant gap in NLP support for low-resource languages, we demonstrate that adapting an existing multilingual model with high-quality domain-diverse Macedonian text can yield strong performance improvements

across core language understanding and reasoning tasks. Our evaluation shows that despite its smaller size, VezilkaLLM performs competitively with larger models, confirming that focused pretraining is a viable strategy for linguistic adaptation in underrepresented languages.

This work contributes not only a practical foundation model for Macedonian NLP, but also a replicable framework for adapting LLMs to other low-resource settings with minimal computational overhead. The open release of our model and training recipe further supports transparency, reproducibility, and future community-driven development.

Moving forward, several directions remain open for exploration. First, instruction tuning and alignment techniques, such as RLHF or DPO, should be applied to make VezilkaLLM more suitable for real-world interactive applications. Second, domain-specific fine-tuning in fields like law, healthcare, or education could significantly enhance its value for professional use cases. Third, the development of native Macedonian benchmarks, created, validated, and annotated by linguistic experts, would enable more rigorous, culturally contextualized evaluation. Finally, multilingual alignment across closely related South Slavic languages presents an opportunity to build interoperable models capable of transfer learning and cross-lingual understanding.

Through these continued efforts, VezilkaLLM can evolve into a robust and trusted component of the Macedonian NLP ecosystem, while serving as a model for responsible and efficient LLM adaptation in other low-resource language contexts.

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